

Russian nationalism shifting: The role of populism since the Annexation of Crimea.

Sofia Tipaldou (University of Manchester)¹ and Philipp Casula (University of Basel)

Abstract

This article focuses on the on-going war in a borderland between the European Union and Russia, the conflict in Eastern Ukraine (Donbass) that started with the events on the Euromaidan and the swift annexation of Crimea by Russia. Our analysis of key speeches by Vladimir Putin regarding the annexation of Crimea and the war in the Donbass demonstrates that in this case, populism extends beyond the dichotomy of the people against the establishment, since it relies on complex notions of enmity and alliance. We argue that, in the context of Crimea's annexation and the war in Donbass, the Russian political leadership deployed a discourse of Russian identity, which is based on an overstretched definition of the Russian nation, a new discursive division of the political space, and the introduction of new and the reaffirmation of old symbols of unity. We also conclude that populism and nationalism were used interchangeably according to the audience: Russian leadership has used discursive strategies associated with populism to articulate this new vision of identity in relation to Crimean residents, and nationalist ones when addressing the domestic audiences.

Introduction

Putin's Russia "is not a democracy, but it is in the name of the people, and for the people. Putin's main constituency is "the people". All of his power comes from his rating with the people", explains Andranik Migranyan (quoted in Ioffe 2018). Popular legitimacy in Russia, however, is not derived from elections. Since the beginning of his presidency, Vladimir Putin has shaped domestic policies that have not only emphasized elements of patriotism (Sakwa 2004: 166), xenophobia, especially against migrants (Tipaldou & Uba 2014: 1091-3) and anti-Westernism (Verkhovsky 2007), but also of depoliticization (Makarychev 2008) and populism (Casula 2013; 2017). The notion of populism points in a different direction than the study of nationalism or democracy and begs the question: who precisely is "the people" who so matters to the Russian political leadership?

Russian official discourse under Putin has carefully disentangled ethnicity from national identity, and has introduced into its definition of Russianness a mixture of pre-Soviet and Soviet symbols (Fish 2001, 2017: 67; Sakwa 2004: 169; Laruelle 2009: 153- 174; Tipaldou 2015: 186-188). Putin's way of conducting politics has led scholars to compare him to well-established populist politicians such as Hugo Chavez, Umberto Bossi, and Geert Wilders (Fella & Ruzza 2009, 2013; Fish 2017:68).

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His late political opponent Boris Nemtsov has also accused Putin of “pursuing a policy of warlike populism in order to bolster his approval ratings” (Arjakovsky 2017). Warlike situations imply a populist dichotomization of political space. For Putin as a regular pursuer of antagonistic politics, politics is the continuation of war, to use Foucault’s (1980: 90) famous inversion of Clausewitz’s statement: at the beginning of his tenure, Putin’s key to winning over large segments of the Russian population was the declaration of war against crime, a “dictatorship of law”, which divided up the political space into order and chaos. He then connected his name with the war in Chechnya, i.e. against one of the Russian Federation’s own federal subjects. The Chechen war has split the political space into terrorists and their opponents and has triggered one of the bloodiest conflicts of post-Soviet Russia (see also Hale 2000).

Fourteen years later, Russia is again at the center of a war in the post-Soviet space. As with the Chechen conflict, the war in the Donbass is shrouded with a mixture of nationalism and populism that has triggered a “rally ‘round the flag syndrome” (Mueller 1970) in Russia. In contrast to the Chechen war that could draw on a religious narrative as well, pitting Orthodox Russians against Muslim Chechens, the people to whom the Russian State appealed during the Crimean crisis and the subsequent war in the Donbass was a much more unstable, slippery, and problematic construct, since Ukrainians were considered a brotherly Slavic nation. These “brothers”, to some extent also including Crimea’s Muslim Tatars, had to be won over. This could not be achieved through the use of exclusive nationalism² by the Russian government. Hence, official discourse activated the most populist and inclusionary elements of a tamed, official Russian nationalism (Kolstø and Blakkisrud 2018: 8).

The special bond between Ukraine and Russia, cultivated through centuries (especially by Russia), grants the Crimean and Donbass conflicts their exceptionality and constitutes the puzzle that the present investigation seeks to fathom. Against this backdrop, the research questions this article seeks to answer are: How can Vladimir Putin justify intervention in Crimea and war in the Donbass against Ukraine, if the image of an “antagonistic Other” is blurred, and if the Other does somehow belong to the Self? What frames does the discourse he represents use to construct the features of the people to whom it wants to appeal? To answer these questions, we conduct a thematic analysis of Vladimir Putin’s key 2014 speeches to get a clearer picture of the people and its allies and friends, the enemies, and the symbols that are used to keep “the people” united. We have selected these speeches because they were delivered at a particular historical juncture, in the context of the annexation of Crimea and the beginning of the war in the Donbass. This selection offers rich empirical data to detail the dominant conception of the membership of the Russian nation and can hence be considered particularly revealing about the populism-nationalism nexus in contemporary Russian politics, at this specific moment in time. All three constituent parts of populism – the people, the enemies, and the symbols (Laclau 2005) – are defined differently than in nationalism. In some instances, however, Russian nationalism and populism overlap, especially when governmental discourse

2 We use the term nationalism in Anthony Smith’s (2001) sense, i.e. as an ideological movement for attaining as maintaining autonomy, unity, and identity for a population which some of its members deem to constitute an actual or potential ‘nation’ according to narrowly ethnic terms or broader civic criteria, like belonging to a state.

returns to a pre-revolutionary definition of the Russian nation, one that was rejected under the Soviet regime.

Our analysis shows that the dichotomic separation of identities between “us” and “them” does not grasp the whole complexity of the issue. We argue that Vladimir Putin’s selective use of an overstretched definition of the Russian nation, a new officially-endorsed discursive division of political space, and the introduction of new and a reaffirmation of old symbols of unity are constitutive of a new pan-Russian identity regarding the annexation of Crimea and later the war in the Donbass. Furthermore, we show that “populism” is used when “nationalism” no longer fits and that it provides Russia with a “non-ethnic nationalism” that seeks to unify the Eurasian nations under Russian leadership.

Studying Putin’s discursive strategies towards Ukraine, the way he constructs a people, advances our knowledge of the relation between nationalism and populism as strategies to sustain the power of the political elites, and is of utmost importance to the understanding of European populist movements, to which Putin’s Russia entertains tight connections. Taggart (2004) and Wejnert (2014: 156) argue that the flexibility of populism makes it particularly apt for sustaining all kinds of policies. Populism can be an oppositional, a democratic, and an emancipatory movement, as Laclau (2005) emphatically argued, but it can also be a tool in tension with democracy (Wejnert 2014). The crucial element for the present article is populism’s capacity to construct “the people”, or “the in-group” (Woods 2014:12), that is pitted against an outside enemy, as will be discussed in detail below. The study of populism in Russia has so far been widely neglected when compared with discussion of populist movements in Western Europe or Latin America (Laclau 1978; Conniff 2012; De la Torre & Arnson 2013). The dominant paradigm for looking at politics in Russia has been nationalism or (non-) democracy, despite the central role that populism has been acknowledged to play in neo-authoritarian regimes (e.g. Venezuela, China). Furthermore, we can expect that the populist narrative used by the Russian government to define “the people” will have repercussions in the field of foreign policy (Faizullaev & Cornut 2016), as populism can also be transnational, with appeals being made to foreign audiences, not least by the Russian international media: Yablokov (2015: 302) explicitly links a Laclauian notion of populism to the strategies pursued in conspiracy theories as aired by RT. Thus, this article is relevant not only for scholars of populism, but also for scholars of foreign policy and policy makers.

The article is structured as follows; first, we introduce relevant aspects of the theoretical debate on populism and foreign policy, we advance a working definition of populism, and the criteria, which we use as the basis to extract data from the key governmental speeches that we have chosen. Second, in the empirical section, we discuss populism in three parts. The first part presents the notion of “the people” that Putin has unfolded; the second part discusses the division of political space he sketches, i.e. who the enemies of the people are; and the third part presents the collective symbols that he proposes to unify the people. Finally, we scrutinize the populist features of Putin’s discourse regarding the war in Ukraine.

Populism and nationalism: conceptual and methodological remarks

In this section, we discuss the complex relationship between nationalism and populism, unfolding the different layers of the connection between the two. Since this is not deemed to be a theoretical article, we aim at a tentative working definition of this connection. The way that populist leaders frame politics can often result in polarization (Taggart 2017). War and armed conflict need such a polarized condition of “us against them”. Defining “the people” is central, because narratives are used as instruments of political reasoning and persuasion as Faizullaev and Cornut (2016) have shown in their analysis of the antagonistic narrative practices used in international politics such as the case of Crimea’s annexation.

The Ukrainian crisis has opened up a space in which the populist dimension of current Russian politics has come to the fore. Indeed, the official narrative defining ‘us’ and ‘them’, against the backdrop of the intricately intertwined history of Russia and Ukraine, had emerged first. Put differently, official discourse had created “a people” that subsequently became policy and, ultimately an ad hoc constituency in the conflict with Ukraine. Teper (2016) has shown how in Russian state-controlled broadcasting the focus of official Russian identity discourse has shifted from the state to the nation. Hutchings and Szostek (2015) have presented the dominant narratives in Russian political and media discourse during the Ukraine crisis, which are linked to Russia’s “grand nation-building mission”, an idea that has intensified significantly under Putin. Contrary to this argument, we see populism as Putin’s major tool for perpetuating power and national glory as only one feature of his populism, the loss of which threatens his regime (Aron 2017: 79; Fish 2017: 66). Populism and nationalism are different, however. According to Yannis Stavrakakis (2005: 245-246):

“although both (...) populism and nationalism share an equivalential logic, they are, firstly, articulated around different *points de capiton* (the nation and the people, respectively) and secondly, [they] construct a very different enemy as their antagonistic ‘other’: in the case of nationalism the enemy to be opposed is usually another nation, while in the case of populism the enemy is of an internal type: the power-bloc, the ‘privileged’ sectors, and so on”.

In turn, Paul Taggart argues that nationalism and populism are “distinct concepts and that attachment to either of them can have very different consequences” (Taggart 2000: 96). Put differently, with populism it is possible to identify enemies within the nation, and friends outside the nation. While nationalism has a delineated constituency (Taggart 2000: 116), populism has not. Its constituency is purely “political” and it requires a political operation to bind and keep this constituency together. Taggart (2000: 73) underscores the anti-institutional politics of populism in general and argues that “populism has real difficulties in regularizing itself as political practices, institutions and regimes” (Taggart 2000: 59). However, he fails to analyze precisely *how* populism institutionalizes itself and the examples he cites (mainly Peronism) point more in the direction of an autocratic and charismatic leadership.

Ernesto Laclau (2005) has developed a purely formal conception of populism, not describing it as a movement with a specific content and a specific constituency - such as the nation in nationalism, the peasants for the *Narodniki*, or the working class in socialism - but as a political logic, form, style, or mechanism. Politically, Laclau sees populism as an emancipatory force from below, in which underdogs unite and rise against an unresponsive institutionalized system, but his framework largely ignores populism in power. Despite Laclau's focus on populism as a movement from below, his formal analysis allows us to trace elements of populism also when it does not come as a popular movement from below, but as a strategy "from above". Although Laclau's definition is a far more complex one, we will narrow it down to three elements that stand out and use these three elements for our empirical analysis.

The first crucial element in Laclau's approach is to see the people not as a given, a pre-existing entity whom, for instance, "populist" politicians can address, whose pre-existing interests they can represent. Inasmuch as it seems to clearly differ from nationalism, which assumes a mythical, ethnically pure entity that existed before political struggles or economic modernization. Most nationalists believe its people has existed ever since. Populists do mostly not. For scholars of populism like Ernesto Laclau, the people is instead a political category, a political subjectivity that has to come into being (Laclau 2005: 224). Hence, this notion allows us to think more flexibly about what kind of "people" might be constituted in our empirical material. This is a particularly important aspect in the Soviet and post-Soviet context both of which have always operated with different notions of the people, such as *russkii narod*³, *rossiiskii narod*, *sovetskii narod* with the latter two being the result of a fusion of different peoples (Kandiyoti 2002: 290; Simonsen 1996: 91; Tolz 2011: 36; for general attributes of "the people" in Russian official discourse: Gavrilova 2015).

The second crucial feature of such a conception of populism is the establishment of a dichotomic frontier, which splits the "political space" and separates "the people" from a common enemy. War is a typical situation, which leaves no room for third options, and in which the political space is indeed reduced to an "Us vs. Them". This mechanism is similar to how nationalism operates, but here the dichotomization is not based on nationality, ethnicity, or race.

The third feature has to do with the means that can unify the people and that can hold these various segments and demands together. Symbols are the "glue" that unites disparate agendas and discursive elements into one populist discourse. This "glue" is needed because "the people" is diverse and "filled" with a variety of possibly incoherent demands. Hence, symbols act as nodal points that keep these demands together. In contrast to nationalism, populism lacks a foundational myth, it cannot refer to a shared ancestry, or to ties of blood. It nevertheless needs symbols similar to those present in nationalism. However, in populism these are much more spontaneous and situational. In populism, collective symbols must arise that galvanize all the demands of a populist discourse. Also, a populist leader must emerge, whose name can immediately bring to mind each single demand in the discourse.

³ *Narod* in Russian can mean both the people and the nation (Tolz 2011: 32).

Based on these three features, we track down through thematic analysis the agendas and demands that are raised in Russian official discourse in the context of the Crimean crisis and how this discourse has contributed to the emergence of a new notion of “the people”. Our research seeks to grasp the emergence and development of this new concept from the political elite; therefore we examine the Russian president’s most significant speeches during the year that the crisis spilled over from Euromaidan to Crimea to Eastern Ukraine: 2014. Our research aims to establish how this idea was presented to both domestic and international audiences.

Against this backdrop, we selected four speeches by Vladimir Putin, which were delivered as the events on Crimea unfolded: 1) Putin reply to journalists’ questions on the situation in Ukraine on 4 March 2014; 2) The “Crimea Speech” of 18 March 2014; 3) the “Valdai speech” of 24 October 2014; and 4) the *Pryamaya Linea* Q&A of 17 April 2014. The first two, the session with journalists on Ukraine and the “Crimea Speech”, were staged with a focus on Ukraine and were intended to inform both domestic and international audiences about Russia’s position towards Ukraine. The last two, the Valdai speech and *Pryamaya Linea*, take place annually with the aim of targeting international experts on foreign policy and the Russian electorate respectively, but at the critical conjuncture of 2014 they both addressed the issue of Ukraine which is the main reason for this deliberate selection. These four speeches are significant, first, because of the historical moment at which they were delivered – at a time of crisis and of the takeover of territory, these speeches had to address the kind of nationalism or populism that the Russian states pursues, and accordingly, how to justify this policy; secondly, all of them contain a specific vision of “the people” to which Russia wants to relate and which Russian policy aims to address. Hence, the speeches reveal the relation between Russian populism and nationalism in relation to Ukraine at a very precise moment in history.

We extract various demands, agendas, and identities from these speeches based on the distinction between a nationalist and a populist discourse; the former makes national or ethnic demands, the latter constructs a people unifying different demands, as we will see, based on a putative common enmity. “The people”, however, is a slippery concept that can be used by text producers and politicians to conceal power relations through a presentation of an “Us vs. Them distinction” (Machin and Mayr 2012: 84). Finally, we spot different elements, which do not necessarily belong together, but achieve meaning only in relation to one another within a discourse (Laclau 2005: 73). That is, these discursive elements are politically linked together. A good example of this is the connection that Putin establishes between the Second World War and the annexation of Crimea in 2014, which corresponds to the widespread (Russian) practice of constructing historical narratives (Malinova and Casula 2009: 295-301; Malinova 2008).

In accordance with the three components of populism outlined above, we analyze three sets of problems in Russian official discourse in the context of the Ukrainian crisis in order to assess the extent to which it features a populist setup. Firstly, we identify the collective political subject that has been established, or, to put it differently, which “people” is at stake. The Ukrainian case is intriguing, because in Russia there is a long tradition of considering Ukraine, and especially Kyiv, as the cradle of the Russian

state. Additionally, to further legitimize the swallowing up of Crimea into the Russian Federation, a new definition of Russianness had to be presented, one that goes beyond simple ethnic nationalism and perpetuates the 19th century image of Crimea as part of Russian national space. Even more so, now, it was Crimea in particular that was said to be the cradle of Russia, as will be discussed below. Within the context of the referendum, all sorts of grievances, demands, and complaints from the Crimean population, that Kyiv had failed to address, were united into a single front to help form a new political subject. For the same reason, both populism and nationalism were used interchangeably, according to the receivers: a populist discourse in relation to Crimean residents and a nationalist one when addressing the domestic audiences (Teper 2016).

Secondly, we analyze the binary political situation in which this political subject had to be placed and for which referenda are particularly apt. The division of the political space took many forms, among them an opposition between the Crimean people and the Kyiv elites, who were cast as unresponsive to Crimean and later Donbass demands. The division was also couched in national, linguistic and political terms, as we will outline below.

Thirdly, we present the collective symbols used for creating this new political subject. During the crisis many collective symbols, slogans and leaders emerged, such as the slogan *Krymnash* (“Crimea is ours”); the Saint George’s ribbons or *lentochnki*, which predate WWII but became a symbol of victory in 1945, and today serve as a wider symbol of Russian patriotism; Crimea prosecutor Natalia Poklonskaia, who rose to be a YouTube-star; Vladimir Putin himself; and the enigmatic Donbass commander Igor Strelkov. Finally, the conflict witnessed the resurrection of communist symbols, such as the very name of Donetsk and Lugansk “people’s republics” that make direct reference to the Soviet Union, as well as the portrayal of Putin as a wise decision maker in the state-sponsored documentary “The road to Crimea” that draws parallels with how Stalin was portrayed prior to Khrushchev’s de-Stalinization policy.

The use of populism in Russia’s policies in Eastern Ukraine – The people

In Russian official discourse, as expressed by speeches of Vladimir Putin here under scrutiny, ‘the Russian people’ is defined in a manner that combines a generic and yet multiple vision of Russianness. Russians are for Putin a multinational people, an understanding based on both a pre-Soviet Russian definition of the peoples’ spiritual fusion (*dukhovnoe sliianie*) and the emergence of a Soviet people (Tolz 2011: 36). Putin points to the fact that the different ethnic groups, nations and nationalities that live in Russia are held together by their common cultural and “very powerful genetic code”, which encompasses the whole Russian world (*Russkii mir*). For instance, people belonging to the Russian world are united by a distinct morality; they are connected by a vision of the collective that goes beyond the individual. Other values, such as giving one’s life for a friend or for the homeland, form the backbone of Russian patriotism. Putin claims: “we are less pragmatic, less calculating than representatives of other peoples, and we have bigger hearts. Maybe this is a reflection of the grandeur of our country and its boundless expanses. Our people have a more generous spirit” (Putin 2014c). Hence, it is not nationality, ethnicity or language that

determine Russianness but a set of qualities and values. This rhetoric that shifts the attention from racial to civic characteristics is widely used by Western European nationalist groups, e.g. British, Greek, and shows that populist and nationalist claims can, and often do, overlap.

Soviet history is evoked to build up an image of Russians as victimized, as the major victims of Soviet regime repression, of Second World War fascism, and also the greatest victims of the dissolution of the USSR. Russians appear as a disenfranchised, disadvantaged and even oppressed people - all peoples suffered with the breakup of the Soviet Union, Putin contends, but Russians above all. Following Putin: “millions of people went to bed in one country and awoke in different ones” (Putin 2014b).

Putin frames Ukraine in cordial terms; it is not only a neighbor, but also “a brotherly neighboring republic”, “a friendly country”, Ukrainians “are all equal in our eyes, all brothers to us”. Putin states straightforwardly that Russia will not fight against the Ukrainian people (Putin 2014a). Ukrainians, according to Putin, are the people with whom Russians have close historical, cultural and economic ties. This statement highlights the interconnectedness between the two nations in historical, emotional, and pragmatic terms. “The people in Ukraine are Russia’s friends”, Putin claims. Putin considers what the role of “a good neighbor and the closest relative” of Ukraine should be and expresses his hope that the people in Ukraine will understand that Russia could not do otherwise with Crimea and that they will respect the choices of Crimean residents (Putin 2014c).

Putin does not stop there. He presents himself, instead, as a fighter for the Ukrainians’ rights, by stressing that corrupt politicians in Ukraine have “milked the country, fought among themselves for power”. He expresses an understanding of “peaceful slogans against corruption, inefficient state management and poverty”, exploiting the diversity of the Maidan movement (Onuch & Sasse 2016). Putin also wants to be the leader of these “ordinary” people’s fight against a corrupt political elite, and he claims to effectively act as such with the Crimeans (Putin 2014b). For Putin, it is the government of Ukraine that has failed, and not the Ukrainian people. Putin, therefore, claims to sympathize with Ukraine, which is a “long-suffering land” that is experiencing the re-emergence of nationalism and neo-Nazism in its western territories (Putin 2014c).

Putin also appeals to the Ukrainian military by stating that the armed forces are “comrades-in-arms, friends, many of whom know each other personally” (Putin 2014a). He evokes common military experiences, especially of the top-echelons of both armed forces, such as the Soviet military mission in Afghanistan. The “peaceful” annexation of Crimea, Putin claims, is a major expression of this unity between the two armies. These two armies, these two peoples are for Putin essentially one army and one people. After all, according to Putin, the events in Crimea were an attempt to overthrow the government by a “group of armed men” in an unconstitutional fashion, with Western backing. The Crimean people, however, set up “self-defense committees” and took control of all the armed forces in Crimea (Putin 2014a).

In these statements, however, Putin also starts splitting the Ukrainian population. He claims that the situation in central, eastern and south-eastern Ukraine is “another matter” than in the rest of the country.

These territories that for Putin constitute *Novorossiia*,⁴ were given to Ukraine in the 1920s by the Soviet government and have intertwined their roots with Russia. *Novorossiia*'s residents "have a somewhat different mentality" which makes it difficult for them to establish relations with the West. Putin also mentions the ethnic composition of Crimea as a point of difference from southeastern Ukraine (Putin 2014c).

As far as the Crimean people is concerned, Putin unfolds a highly complex notion that sets the speech apart from simple Russian nationalism and irredentism. "The people of Crimea", who are "the ultimate source of all authority", are a "unique blend of different people's cultures and traditions". However, he mentions only three groups, Russians, the Ukrainians who predominantly consider Russian their native language, and Crimean Tatars. In his own words: "Crimea was and remains a Russian, Ukrainian, and Crimean-Tatar land" (Putin 2014b). In contrast to Teper's (2016) TV coverage descriptions, here Putin draws on a mixture of imperial thinking and populism, as "the people" he refers to, now relates to the Russian Empire. Tatars might have suffered under Stalinism, but so did all nationalities - and above all the ethnic Russians. Thus, Putin not only diminishes the injustices suffered by the Tatars, but he generally essentializes the ethnic set-up of the peninsula and reduces it linguistically to Russophones and Tatars.

The separation of Crimea from Russia enacted under Nikita Khrushchev has been, for Putin, the result of bad decisions taken by bad politicians. After the Bolsheviks, who added without consideration large sections of Russia's "historical South" to the Republic of Ukraine, it was Khrushchev who transferred Crimea to Ukraine for dubious reasons. Putin depicts these decisions as ill-guided, contrary to common-sense and the will of the people. Thus, the annexation of Crimea becomes the expression of a popular will, a rebellion against bad decisions taken by former politicians. People had hoped for a new political entity that would replace the USSR and had hoped the CIS would fulfill such a role (Putin 2014b).

Putin (2014c) stresses that Russians are "native persons in Ukraine", adding a new twist to the interconnectedness between Russians and Ukrainians in the post-Soviet space. The people whom Putin claims responsibility for are *all Russians everywhere*, including those in Ukraine. Especially in Crimea, a large part of the population speaks Russian. As the Ukrainian government could not provide a sufficient level of security, Russia had to step in, Putin explains. Russia always hoped that all *native Russians* – the Russian-speaking people living in Ukraine – would live in a comfortable political environment (Putin 2014c).

It is in these sections where the careful balance Putin tries to establish between all people of the USSR and all people of Crimea, tips in the direction of a hardly veiled preference for ethnic Russians, whose rights Putin claims to restore by "returning" Crimea to Russia. This return of Crimea to Russia is presented as a small step in a larger process of bringing the CIS countries closer together, by broadening the conception of Russianness, by arguing for a broader, more inclusive of whom can call herself or himself "Russian" (*russkii*). It was precisely this aim that lay behind the proposed Eurasian Union, pursued in the

4 Here Putin - accidentally or not - includes also central Ukraine in the definition of *Novorossiia*.

years before the Euromaidan, and which the Euromaidan, the annexation of Crimea and the war in the Donbass thwarted (Putin 2014b). As such, Putin is cast as a leader of “Ukraine and Russia” and of “Eurasian integration”. In this sense, “the people” in this speech means the Eurasian people as a whole and not just Russians, Ukrainians and Russophones, who “live in Ukraine and will continue to do so”. With the return of Crimea as “common historical legacy” to Russia, Putin can restore a small piece of the Soviet Union (Putin 2014b). In this multinational vision, however, Russians come first, and it is Russians who determine which peoples have the right to exist and how they are to live (Putin 2014b).

The use of populism in Russia’s policies in Eastern Ukraine – The enemies

In all of his speeches under scrutiny, Putin alludes to a number of different enemies. Here, we introduce the distinction between temporal categories of enemies (past vs. present), and spatial (inside vs. outside) ones. As a matter of fact, in the discourse, which Putin deploys, time and space are blurred. Putin leaves unclear whether Ukraine and the Ukrainians are inside or outside the state entity and the community he addresses. In a populist guise, he also declares certain social strata (the establishment) to be foes of the people. Most surprisingly, we find the Russian president listing several unlikely “enemies of the past”. He accuses the Bolsheviks and the Soviet leadership under Nikita Khrushchev of crimes against popular common sense. Both allegedly took decisions, which ran against the will of the people and against objective ethnic divides: Khrushchev when he gave Crimea to Ukraine, and the early Bolsheviks when they established new administrative borders within the USSR (Putin 2014b).

The reactionary, nationalist and anti-Semitic forces in certain parts of Ukraine can be described as “enemies of the future” and are represented by the new Ukrainian authorities who are pronounced “Nationalists, neo-Nazis, Russophobes and anti-Semites”, murderers, terrorists, radicals and rioters. However, the enemies of the future have a close relationship with other enemies of the past, who were foes of the USSR and are personified in the figure of Stepan Bandera, Hitler’s accomplice in Ukraine during the Second World War (Teper 2016: 386). Putin even compares certain participants in the Euromaidan protests with Nazi storm troopers and makes reference to neo-Nazis in western Ukraine. In the case of Ukraine, it seems that by demanding fundamental political reform, the people let the genie of fascism out of the bottle: “we see them today, people wearing armbands bearing something resembling swastikas still roaming around Kyiv at this moment”. In Putin’s understanding, thus, the past enemies of the USSR could also serve as Ukraine’s future enemies (Putin 2014c; 2014d).

However, the presidential discourse is not free from a spatial categorization of enemies. Some of them are even on the inside of the audience addressed, within the Self. They are subsequently externalized by ascribing to them a political status of traitors – in populism, this would be the establishment that betrayed the people. The first and foremost enemy of the present is the (new) Ukrainian political class. As Putin describes it, one set of thieves has been replaced by another set of thieves, and oligarchs, the product of a “dishonest privatization”, are taking over political positions (i.e. Kolomoisky as Governor of Dnepropetrovsk). Putin claims that “people” dislike the fact that the Kyiv-appointed oligarchs became the

new governors. The “real problem” is that previous Ukrainian governments failed to pay proper attention to the people and thus disappointed them (Putin 2014b). Another issue that concerns “the citizens of Ukraine, both Russian and Ukrainian, and the Russian-speaking population in the eastern and southern regions of Ukraine” is uncontrolled crime. Putin portrays Russia as the unlikely champion of the Ukrainian people’s cause and refers to his alleged accomplishments in ridding Russia of corrupt politicians, oligarchs and crime (Putin 2014a).

Additionally, Putin claims to “understand why Ukrainian people wanted change. They have had enough of the authorities who have been in power during the years of Ukraine’s independence”, as they have only cared about “power, assets and cash flows and not about ordinary people” (Putin 2014c). Furthermore, the Ukrainian state and its political class has become Russia’s enemy since it has sent in tanks and aircrafts and has committed “one more serious crime” against its people (Putin 2014c). Finally, nationalist groups did not surrender their weapons and they threatened to use force in the eastern regions, in response to which inhabitants of the eastern zones started to arm themselves (Putin 2014c).

Another set of enemies are indeed “external enemies”, although the lines between the interior and the exterior are blurred. “External” here means outside Russia and outside Ukraine. Foreign enemies are the West, the “foreign sponsors” of the newly emerging politicians in Ukraine. “Western Europe and North America” turn against Russia, against the incorporation of Crimea into Russia and the popular will. They support the enemies of the inseparable Ukrainian and Russian peoples. Western countries, Putin stresses, “have lied to us many times, made decisions behind our backs, placed us before accomplished facts”, and, citing Kosovo’s independence, selectively interpret international law (Putin 2014c). According to Putin, Russia did not start “this”. Russia has, instead, informed its American and European partners not to proceed with “hasty backstage decisions” on Ukraine’s association agreement with the EU, because they are a serious threat to Ukraine’s economy and to Russia’s interests as Ukraine’s main trade partner (Putin 2014d).

But Russia’s top external enemy is the United States, which has declared itself the winner of the Cold War. As such, the US has not seen the need for carrying out a rational reconstruction and for adapting the system of international relations to new realities. Putin accuses the US of behaving “the way *nouveaux riches* behave when they suddenly end up with a great fortune” and calls it the “big brother” who is spending billions of dollars on keeping the world under surveillance. The US establishment as the world’s “sole power center” has led to the construction of a unipolar world that is unable to deal with the “real threats”, such as regional conflict, terrorism, drug trafficking, religious fanaticism, chauvinism and neo-Nazism. It has led instead to inflated national pride, the manipulation of public opinion and to the suppression of the weak by the strong in the international domain (Putin 2014d).

The final enemy of the present is the West in general, especially as embodied by NATO. NATO broke its promise, Putin argues, not to expand beyond its eastern borders and incorporated former Warsaw Treaty member-countries and the Baltic states, instead. So, Russia is facing the immediate threat of “being really ousted from this region that is extremely important for us”. Putin emphasizes the double standards

that the Western-dominated international community promotes; the US is allowed to intervene in countries such as Yugoslavia, Iraq, Afghanistan, and Libya, but it is considered inappropriate for Russia to “defend its interests”, with Kosovo as the most significant example (Putin 2014c). Putin also complains that Russia’s “Western partners” refused to have talks with Russia about Ukraine’s association agreement; instead they decided to overthrow the government and plunge Ukraine into chaos, “into a civil war with enormous casualties”. In the end, he claims, everyone is at a loss with this situation. Neither did Western countries pursue a dialogue between the Eurasian and the European Union. Russia, however, insists that the only way of ensuring state sovereignty is through continuing talks and not through armament.

The use of populism in Russia’s policies in Eastern Ukraine – The symbols

In the context of the Crimean crisis and the war in the Donbass, a massive surge of symbols has taken place.⁵ Everything started with “polite little green men” popping up at various spots in Crimea: these “military men” looked like elite assault troops, dressed in special uniforms, helmets, protective glasses, knee pads, holding automatic rifles. Many people thought them to be Russian troops, but there were some doubts, as they bore no national insignia. According to Alexei Yurchak, at the beginning, this was a pure, naked military force – “a force without a state, without a face, without identity,” with whom, hence, everybody could potentially identify, irrespective of nationality. This applied to Russians and Ukrainians - the latter have an army in a particularly difficult state - as well as to Crimeans, whose “self-defense forces” looked like and acted “as a motley crew of civilians in camouflage, sportsmen in tracksuits and self-styled Cossacks in grotesque uniforms” (Yurchak 2014). The little green men represented pure military prowess. When it was eventually revealed that these were Russian special operation forces, they contributed to the image of an advanced military power that had fully overcome the trauma of the past and the embarrassing defeats in Chechnya. This was a new Russian force, a new Russian man, a new Russian power that was unfolding in Crimea and whom many Russian men were proud of in the blogosphere (Yurchak 2014). They also stood in contrast to the Ukrainian armed forces, whose combat readiness was comparatively low.

The very manly, professional and strong “little green men” stand in contrast to another symbol of the early phase of the Ukraine crisis, Natalia Poklonskaia. While the highly trained Russian soldiers represented a resurgent, strong Russia, Poklonskaia was the weak, victimized, threatened, female Russian-Ukrainian fusion in danger, about whom Putin (2014) spoke as well. On 11 March, Poklonskaia was appointed Prosecutor General of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea. On this occasion, the young, newly appointed female prosecutor gave a defiant press conference, repeating the tenets of Russian official discourse, stating the unconstitutionality of the coup in Kyiv, to which she also referred as an armed seizure of power. Ukraine’s new parliamentarians were, for her, “devils from the ashes.” At the same time, the speech was clumsy and emotional.

⁵ The authors categorize under symbols both human and material objects, being aware that there is a difference in their sources of symbolization, because they emphasize on the emotions that these symbols provoke and not their source as such.

Poklonskaia was appointed after other candidates refused the post and displayed uneasiness with the task. It is this mix of defiance and insecurity that was crucial for her symbolic value. Furthermore, like Crimea itself, she switches sides from Ukraine to Russia, and like for Crimea while pledging allegiance, she begged for Moscow's protection. Poklonskaia also fits into the narrative of a female, victimized Russia that was under threat from fascism, in danger of being attacked and raped by Banderists as in the Second World War – this is the same narrative that Putin (2014b) employed in his 2014 Address, which was riddled with allusions to that war. Like all Crimeans, it seemed, she refused the “coup” in Kyiv and just wanted the same key promises that Putin gave to Russia as a whole when he became president: law and order, security, the “dictatorship of law”, a longing for the reestablishment of pride. In later speeches, Poklonskaia came back to the topics so dear to Russian official discourse. She claimed that “Ukraine, Russia, Belarus – all came from one big country – the USSR (...) Therefore, the fundamental principle of law, the requirements that comply with all international regulations, they are the same.” (Russia Today 2014). It is the manly, strong and heroic little green men that represent the heroic, masculine side of Russia that save Poklonskaia from “fascism”. Today, Poklonskaia is a parliamentarian in the State Duma and advocates a religiously grounded Russian nationalism.

Another key symbol became the bridge connecting Russia and Crimea, opened ahead of time by Vladimir Putin in a media stunt, in May 2018, driving a Kamaz truck from the mainland to Crimea (Horton 2018). The highly expensive (4.5 billion USD) and symbolic project meant that funds had to be redirected: as some observers claim, money was taken from the Russian Railroad pension fund (Elia 2017), or from projects in other underdeveloped regions, especially the Caucasus republics. These republics then craved for Moscow's attention by sending troops to Syria (Bergman 2017, RBK 2017, Casula 2017). Earlier, an interactive exhibition at Moscow's GUM store had been put on to underline the importance of the bridge by underscoring not only that projects to build a bridge have existed at various points in history, but also that Crimea has always been an integral part of Russia: “The historical part of the display tells about the timeline of the linking-up of the two coasts of the Kerch Strait from the time of Prince Gleb to our day and the various stages of the construction of the Crimean bridge” (author's observation).

And finally, Crimea itself became a symbol in populist discourse that was able to unite various groups, nationalities, and demands. In his “Crimean speech”, Putin (2014b) stresses the cultural and symbolic significance of Crimea for Russians, Ukrainians and Belarusians alluding to the baptism of Prince Vladimir in Crimea, and the suffering Crimea endured during the Russian Empire and the Second World War. And Sevastopol, in particular, is used as the symbol of “Russian naval glory, which every Russian citizen knows about” (Putin 2014c). But probably the most powerful symbol is “the Russian-speaking Crimea”. It is this symbol that creates and unites the “people” Putin addresses:

“Everything in Crimea speaks of our shared history and pride. This is the location of the ancient Kherones, where Prince Vladimir was baptized. His spiritual feat of adopting Orthodoxy predetermined the overall basis of the culture, civilization and human values that unite the peoples of Russia, Ukraine and Belarus. The graves of Russian soldiers

whose bravery brought Crimea into the Russian Empire are also in Crimea. This is also Sevastopol – a legendary city with an outstanding history, a fortress that serves as the birthplace of Russia’s Black Sea Fleet. Crimea is Balaklava and Kerch, Malakhov Kurgan and Sapun Ridge. Each one of these places is dear to our hearts, symbolizing Russian military glory and outstanding valor.” (Putin 2014b).

Putin mixes everything in this stretch of his speech. Crimea is about culture and values, about Russia, Ukraine and even Belarus, about the 19th century and the Crimean War, as well as about the Second World War and fighting fascism; it is about Orthodox Christianity and Russian military glory. “Crimea” becomes a highly loaded and thus empty signifier, ultimately for Soviet history and for the Soviet people, with emphasis on the Slavic and Christian peoples, but especially for Russians, reflecting a “*primus inter pares*” position attributed to Russians as in Soviet times. After 2014, “*Krymnash*” (literally: “CrimealsOurs”) became in Russian popular parlance an equally empty slogan that was used in everyday-language and on the Russian internet with seriousness and patriotic conviction (“Crimea is ours”) and with irony (“Things went wrong again ... but at least: *Krymnash*”). It also echoes the widely mocked statement by Dmitri Medvedev who told Crimeans: “there is no money, but you be strong” (*deneg net, a vy derzhites*). Through Crimea, Putin addresses both Ukrainians and Russians by underlining that:

“Crimea is our common historical legacy and a very important factor in regional stability. And this strategic territory should be part of a strong and stable sovereignty, which today can only be Russian. Otherwise, dear friends (*I am addressing both Ukraine and Russia*), you and we – the Russians and the Ukrainians – could lose Crimea completely, and that could happen in the near future” (Putin 2014b).

This move constitutes the establishment (or re-establishment) of a shared past, one that ties Ukrainians and Russians together forever. To further stress this bond, the speech mentions that “Kyiv is the mother of Russian cities. Ancient Rus is our common source and we cannot live without each other”, thus denying Ukraine a specific identity and forcing Ukraine into a Russian embrace, in which Kyiv is reduced to a part of Russia and incapable of “giving birth” to something independent – Ukraine is stuck in a colonial situation (Gerasimov & Mogilner 2015). Once more, this means an indirect resurrection of an oppressed Soviet people.

Conclusions

Following a three-dimensional definition of populism, our article has shown that official Russian political discourse has assumed stark populist features in the context of the Crimean crisis and the subsequent war in the Donbass. As with a Laclauian notion of populism “from below”, Putin’s populism “from above” works according to the same logic: it has attempted to construct a people, to divide the political space and create various enemies, and to produce collective symbols. However, this conclusion comes not without a couple of caveats and shows how difficult it is to generalize the model of populism.

Our analysis shows that Putin is at pains to sketch a vision of Ukrainians and Russians as one people, with shared past experiences, with shared symbols, and with common enemies. Thus, internally, Putin homogenizes “the people”, i.e. it presents it as a unified whole, despite internal divisions. Instead of a simplified, i.e. merely ethnic, notion of Russian nationalism Russian official discourse as represented in Putin speeches needed a concept of “a people”, which is broader and in which everybody can be accommodated. This is why Russian ethnic nationalism alone cannot do the job. Putin emerges as a man of the past, oddly addressing the defunct Soviet people time and again, or conflating today’s Russians with the Soviet people – Hrytsak (1998: 276) argues that the present-day “Soviet identity” actually has such a Russian ethnic dimension. What this “people” shares is, beyond a common past, an opposition to certain elites, and certain enemies in the past and in the present. This posture is Putin’s strength but also his weakness. The speeches activate historical narratives but not to portray a “nation” but rather to construct “a people”.

Following the logic of populism, externally, i.e. for the enemies, Putin perpetuates and essentializes divisions. While Putin claims the West to be the enemy, it is not seen as such by large parts of the Euromaidan-people, while it is more so in the Donbass and in Russia. Invoking the West as the enemy is again a device intended to re-create a *Sovietskii narod* [Soviet people] that felt a common threat. “Bandera”, fascists and anti-Semites are equally mostly the enemies of the defunct Soviet people. However, a very palpable enemy of all within the whole post-Soviet space is the “corrupt elite”. The case of Ukraine was the perfect stage on which to present Putin as a provider of just, fair, and efficient policies in contrast to the Ukrainian politicians, who “robbed” the country. Putin claims to have stood with the people, and the symbols he deployed spoke the same language too: the highly trained and efficient soldiers that occupied key positions in Crimea were a symbol of efficiency that could counter the fragility and weakness of Crimea, embodied by Natalia Poklonskaia. The swift construction of the bridge between mainland Russian and Crimea was yet another sign of Putin’s hands-on attitude that became the symbol of the unity between Crimea and Russia but yet erected another wall against large swathes of the Ukrainian population, which feel increasingly estranged from Russia.

Conceptually, our article shows that the Laclauian notion of populism can direct our analytic attention to things other than the concepts of nationalism or Russian irredentism, or geopolitical considerations. However, it also discusses the limits of this notion. On the one hand, populism can be wielded as much “from above” as “from below”, as long as the official discourse can bind different popular demands and produce leaders. Putin tried to set himself apart from the “corrupt” Ukrainian political establishment, which actually involved adopting the tactic that he had already successfully deployed in Russia (“Putin against the oligarchs”). He has to show that he will be a better leader for Crimea, and possibly of other parts of Ukraine, too. On the other hand, the political space does not split neatly into two halves, even if Putin’s speeches are at pains to suggest this. Rather, the political space is crisscrossed by various demands, which are at times outright nationalist and not just social. We have shown that in line with the bulk of current research on Russian politics, a resurgence of nationalistic themes is certainly taking

place. Indeed, nationalism does not disappear, and it has a role to play in Russian official discourse, in which populist, imperialist and nationalist elements are intertwined. However, so does populism. Through our selection of sources and speeches, held at a crucial moment in the history of the region, we have also deciphered populist themes and discursive strategies that go beyond Russian (ethnic) nationalism to construct a multinational oppressed and victimized people pitted, especially within Ukraine itself, against corrupt elites, “fascism”, and the West.

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